

**ASSESSING THE PT EVOLUTION OF HIGH-PRESSURE MIGMATITIC
PARAGNEISSES VIA THERMODYNAMIC MODELLING (UPPER
ALLOCHTHONOUS UNIT, ÓRDENES COMPLEX, NW IBERIAN MASSIF)**

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In the European continent, the Variscan belt extends from the Iberian Massif to the Bohemian Massif, and is characterized by an internal zone that appears in the core of several allochthonous complexes (Arenas et al., 2016). In the NW of the Iberian Massif, the Órdenes Complex contains an Upper Allochthonous Unit that represents the remnants of a Cambrian magmatic arc located in the periphery of the West African Craton (Gondwana, Albert et al., 2015a,b). This terrane underwent HP-HT metamorphism during the Devonian collision between Gondwana and Laurussia that led to the formation of Pangea. It includes ultramafic rocks, eclogites, granulites and migmatitic paragneisses. The mineral assemblage of the migmatitic paragneisses is composed by garnet+kyanite+biotite+plagioclase+K-feldspar+quartz+rutile+Ti-hematite+melt. Thermodynamic modelling of the measured bulk composition in the NCKFMASHTO system reveals metamorphic peak conditions at ~15 kbar and ~825°C. To assess the prograde evolution of the rocks a melt-reintegration approach is performed. To do so, an internally consistent liquid has been calculated at 11 kbar and 801°C. A 26 element amount % of this liquid has been added to the measured bulk composition to simulate the protolith composition before melting. This melt-reintegrated composition has been modelled, and faced against the earliest metamorphic mineral assemblage developed in the paragneisses to reveal a colder high-pressure event for the paragneisses. Hence a PT trajectory is proposed, which implies the deep subduction of the rocks to mantle depths through a relatively colder path. There, an isobaric heating occurred as a consequence of a long residence time at such depths. A drastic and almost isothermal decompression carried the paragneisses up to the lower crust, where they reached the thermal peak. The final exhumation to shallower levels is characterized by a strong cooling.

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